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ENGINEERING IDENTITY IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

Understanding students' experiences is an integral part of supporting a more diverse student population within the field of engineering. Growing evidence suggests that a greater identification with the engineering profession encourages student persistence. Using identity theory, this study aims to investigate the factors that facilitate the development of engineering identity in undergraduate engineering students using a qualitative research design. Individual interviews with fifteen students in their final year of their engineering programmes provided the primary source of data. The emergent themes explain how students' make sense of their experiences and develop engineering identities as they progress through their engineering degrees. This study provides further insight on student experiences and could inform possible interventions for student retention in engineering programs.

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1 INTRODUCTION

According to Pierrakos et al. (2009), engineering departments are the first concrete contact many high school graduates have with the engineering community. While it is likely learners have interacted with media which centres on engineering or been exposed to the engineering industry through relatives, role models and job shadowing (Jawitz and Case 1998; Reed and Case 2003), tertiary education programmes are still seen as the first essential step to becoming an engineer and developing a professional identity within the engineering community.

1.1 What is an engineering identity?

First-year students start to form a narrative of “What does an engineer do?”; “Who is an engineer?” and “How do I fit into engineering?” These questions are strongly related to students’ professional identity. Engineering students may assume a professional identity of student engineers who will progress to working engineers after graduation and practical training since, as students, they cannot validate themselves as professional engineers (Tonso 2006).

Professional identity has several definitions within engineering education literature with authors describing social and individual dimensions to one’s professional identity (Morelock 2017; Dehing, Jochems, and Baartman 2013). The social dimension makes transparent who is and who is not a professional, visibly regulating the attributes, competencies, values and beliefs of those who define themselves in the profession; while the individual dimension deals with a person’s identification with the profession (Stevens et al. 2008; Tonso 2014).

Using Tonso’s (2014) description of engineering identity, the concept of how an individual perceives themselves in relation to the engineering profession, engineering identity development can thus be seen as an ongoing and complex process that students undergo during their engineering careers, where they frame and re-frame past engineering experiences (Eliot and Turns 2011). Identity theory has a relatively limited application in engineering education settings; however, identity has a strong tradition in the field of psychology.

A useful way of viewing identity is through the lens of narrative identity, a theory drawn from social psychology. McAdams (2011) proposes that people construct evolving stories of themselves to make sense of and give meaning to who they are. This dynamic narrative is a selective reconstruction of past experiences and imagined narrative futures, with an individual’s identity as its product. Engineering identity can thus be seen as an internalised evolving story of the self in relation to their engineering career.

1.2 Why does engineering identity matter?

A number of studies have investigated the process of engineering identity development and the factors that affect students' engineering identity. Morelock (2017) organises these factors into constructive, detractive and directional factors. Accordingly, the constructive factors help students build stronger engineering identities and conversely, the detractive weaken students' identity construction while the directional factors affect the type of identity developed.

Detractive factors can affect students' learning, sense of belonging and persistence in engineering programs. Pierrakos (2009) and Tonso (2014) demonstrate how an individual's identification with engineering can be critical in terms of their persistence, with those who experience a weaker identification with engineering often migrating to other fields. Likewise, graduates strongly identifying as engineers after tertiary programs are more likely to remain in the engineering field, once they enter the workplace (Eliot & Turns, 2011). Additionally, factors that weaken identity construction are often focussed on issues particular to women and black people, with few interventions addressing these issues (Tonso 2014; Morelock 2017).

1.3 Research Question:

Engineering identity research provides a meaningful lens for understanding student experiences, particularly in a South African context which has a diverse, unequal society that is reflected in the student population in engineering programs at universities. From this perspective, the central research question inquires:

“What factors facilitate the development of engineering identity in undergraduate students and what is their impact on students' academic experiences within a South African context?”

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this study draws on ethnographical principles. The fieldwork was conducted by a master's student in engineering education who had recently graduated with an engineering degree. The structure of the engineering programs was therefore well known to the primary researcher. The University of Cape Town (UCT) offers a four year BSc (Eng) degree with the first three years mostly theory-based and the fourth year including a major research project of the student's choice.

With this in mind, invitations to participate in the research study were sent to all final year students in mechanical, electrical, civil and chemical engineering in the last semester of their degrees. There were few responses and consequently most

participants were selected using snowball sampling practices (Creswell 2007) with participants referring others to the study. Of those who were referred, fifteen participants were selected, three students from the electrical engineering department and four students each in the remaining departments.

Participating Students	
Civil	Chantelle, Chris, Luzuko, Sinethemba
Chemical	Marina, Olivia, Scott, Sean
Electrical	Ben, French, Tshepo
Mechanical	Homer, Nosipho, Patricia, Siyamthanda

Table 1: Pseudonyms of participants from engineering departments

The primary source of data was semi-structured interviews (Creswell 2007) with interviews taking place in the third quarter of the academic year. The interview schedule was developed using McAdams' life story interview protocol (McAdams 2008) and was framed by the research question. Interview questions explored students' narrative journeys in relation to engineering and why specific event and actions had greater meaning in their engineering degrees. The interview protocol is attached as an appendix.

Narrative analysis (Polkinghorne 1995) was chosen as the preferred method of data analysis. Interviews were transcribed and then analysed using computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (NVivo). This software offered the researchers a means of storing, retrieving, coding and sorting data. The process of coding was informed by the data analysis method.

Narrative inquiry focuses on personal stories, particularly their structure, content and themes. Plot elements of students' narratives were categorised and thematically analysed in an inductive approach (Andrews, Squire, and Tamboukou 2008). This made it highly suitable for analysing students' narratives in relation to engineering and produced interesting results.

3 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Strong factors were linked to participants' engineering identity construction and several major identity themes emerged from the data. From the fifteen interviews, eight participants described fully developed engineering identities and openly labelled themselves as 'engineers' or 'student engineers'.

While seven participants indicated they would not be pursuing engineering opportunities after graduation and openly labelled themselves as not 'engineers'. Six main factors positively helped participants identify with engineering in varying degrees. These ranged from an interest in disciplinary knowledge, enjoyment in practical experience to engaging with engineering lecturers.

3.1 Constructive factors

Most participants with fully developed engineering identities such as French and Ben² displayed a clear interest in disciplinary knowledge. When asked about their academic experiences, these two electrical engineering students described how their outlook on learning changed from first year to their final year. They stressed the importance of gaining a deeper understanding of engineering concepts rather than just acquiring foundational knowledge for assessment purposes as they had done in their first year.

Part of their transformation was understanding the connections between different engineering courses and how they build on each other. They saw their fourth-year research projects as a natural next step in their learning and were keen to apply their acquired technical knowledge.

French and Ben also recounted their enjoyment of their fourth-year projects. Both participants emphasised the importance of using their technical and design knowledge to solve engineering design problems. While Chantelle, a civil engineering student, described how her positive vacation work experiences helped further her understanding of foundational knowledge.

She described how applying theoretical knowledge to real-world problems, helped her make connections between different engineering concepts and courses. She recounted how the experiences helped her grow personally and understand her role as an engineer better. All these experiences appeared to be crucial in helping participants identify more closely with the engineering profession, with factors falling to the left of the continuum below.

² All names are pseudonyms.

Figure 1. Continuum of factors linked to engineering identity construction.

Engineering connections were also positively linked to engineering identity construction. Sinethemba and Chris, two civil engineering students, spoke about gaining exposure to engineering industries through their bursary programmes. Whereas Chantelle had the benefit of gaining early exposure through her close relatives and learning early on she enjoyed civil engineering. Such connections proved to be important when they decided to pursue engineering. The students had a network of engineering mentors and relatives who could advise them and help them gain practical experience through vacation work opportunities.

When asked about interactions with staff, Nosipho emphasised the importance of engaging with lecturers. The mechanical engineering student described how she started asking questions and interacting with lecturers after a difficult first year. She explained how she had to overcome her inhibitions and realised that asking questions made her a better student and engineer. Seeking advice furthered her understanding of foundational knowledge and helped grow her interest and appreciation for engineering research.

Interactions with peers and study groups were mentioned by both 'student engineers' and 'non-engineers'. This factor was seen as an integral part of one's academic success. Peers and study groups were usually the first place students sought academic advice prior to consulting with lecturers. The majority of participants highlighted how fellow peers emotionally and academically supported each other through their degrees. Developing relationships with staff, mentors and peers

enhanced participants' engineering networks and ended up strengthening their identification with engineering

Another factor that was mentioned by both groups was an interest in social studies particularly those that focused on social issues and inequality. Participants with an interest in social studies showed strong social and political identities. Students with fully developed engineering identities and a social interest were motivated to pursue engineering work that benefited greater society. While this factor strengthened students' identification with engineering, it could also be classified as a directional factor which affects the type of engineering identity developed.

Most of the constructive factors are present in engineering education literature. Two emergent categories arose similar to Morelock's (2017) engineering-related experiences and engineering network. This is important as it speaks to the link between students' academic experiences and engineering identity development. Positive academic activities such as engaging with lecturers, trying to conceptually understand engineering theory and interacting with peers and study groups, resulted in further developed engineering identities. Which means engineering identity can be used as a mediator for one's academic experiences.

Another interesting finding was how an interest in social studies and a strong social identity affected engineering identity. Few studies highlight students' social or political identities impacting engineering identity (Tonso 2014; Morelock 2017) though the appearance of a social identity is understandable within the South African context. The University of Cape Town and other South African universities have faced major protests in recent years. All participants were students during the country-wide #FeesMustFall and #RhodesMustFall university protests and interviews took place just weeks after a gender-based violence protest at UCT. The fact that multiple participants spoke about how social issues impact their views of engineering, shows that engineering identities cannot be divorced from other aspects of an individual's identity.

3.2 Detractive factors

For the seven participants who openly labelled themselves as not 'engineers'. Factors that negatively impacted students' engineering identities often occurred in combination and were frequently linked to students' academic experiences. These ranged from challenging academic demands, to a disinterest in engineering knowledge, to hostile academic environments.

Unsurprisingly, most of these participants were impartial or indifferent towards disciplinary work. Homer, a mechanical engineering student, recounted how he wasn't drawn towards engineering work and would rather work within the financial sector after graduation. While Luzuko in civil engineering mentioned that though he valued the

problem-solving skills he had acquired during his degree, he would rather work in social entrepreneurship. His initial lack of exposure to engineering coupled with his academic struggles added to his disinterest in pursuing civil engineering after graduation. Whereas Rachel cited how a hostile academic environment in mechanical engineering and excessive academic demands in her degree made her wary of entering an engineering workplace. Rachel recounted how she faced gender marginalisation while working with her male peers and added that the stress of getting her degree was not worth continuing with engineering.

The identified detractive factors were unsurprising as many of them were present in engineering education literature. The fact that three of the four detractive factors are based on students' experiences within their degrees underpins the connection between engineering experiences and identity construction. Students' engineering identities can bring to light educational issues and act as a mediator for students' academic experiences.

4 CONCLUSION

While identity research offers a meaningful framework to explore multiple aspects of an individual's experience, few studies are focused on engineering identity in the Global South. In this study, fifteen interviews were conducted with final-year engineering students at a South African university to understand what factors facilitated the development of engineering identity and how they impacted on students' academic experiences. Narrative analysis revealed a range of constructive and detractive factors impacting students' engineering identity.

Most constructive factors were related to students engineering experiences (academic work, vacation work) and their network (peers, lecturers, mentors). Students' engineering identities often developed alongside their personal and social identities. These identities often informed students' engineering identity and motivated them to pursue engineering with a socially engaged focus. In contrast, detractive factors seemed to come in combinations, with negative academic experiences and disinterest in disciplinary knowledge as a popular combination. These factors dissuaded students from seeking engineering opportunities after graduation.

Overall, students with stronger engineering identities had more meaningful engineering experiences in their academic careers and had a stronger engineering network. From these findings, a number of recommendations can be made. Students should be encouraged to participate in engineering-related activities outside of the curriculum such as university engineering societies. They should be encouraged to seek out mentors and roles models, whether other students (undergraduate and postgraduate), academic staff or working engineering professionals. Lastly, further

research is needed to understand engineering identity development and its impact on students, particularly in South Africa and the Global South.

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6 APPENDIX

Interview protocol used during interviews.

Interview Protocol:

I want you to think of the interviews an exploration into your learning journey in engineering. Think of your time at university as a novel, with different chapters and scenes, with high points and low points. We are exploring your story in university and in engineering.

1. Take me back to high school and why did you choose to study engineering?
 - a. Why did you choose your discipline?
 - b. Were you exposed to engineering before coming to university?
 - c. What were your expectations of university and your engineering academic work?
2. What was coming into university like?
 - a. How was the transition from high school to university?
 - b. How did things progress in first year?
 - c. Could you tell me about the parts where you excelled or struggled?
3. How were the middle years? Second and third year?
 - a. Were things different from first year?
 - b. How did your experiences measure up to the expectations?
4. What were your interactions with peers like?
 - a. Did you participate in any study groups or peer networks?
 - b. How were your experiences with group work?
5. What were your interactions with staff members like?
 - a. How were your lecture and tutorial experiences with staff members?
 - b. Did you have any one-on-one or small group (two or three students) meetings with staff members?
6. What experiences (high and low) stand out most for you in your engineering career now that you are nearing graduation?
 - a. Did it influence how you see yourself?
 - b. Did it influence how you see yourself as an engineer?
7. What experience was most important to you in your engineering journey?
 - a. What impact did it have on you as an engineering student?
 - b. Did it influence your career decisions?
 - c. Did it influence how you see yourself?
8. Is there anything you would like to add?